

SUSTAINABLE MYCELIUM-DERIVED CHITINOUS THIN FILMS

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ABSTRACT

Mycelium, the vegetative growth of filamentous fungi, has attracted increasing commercial and academic interest in recent years due to its ability to upcycle agricultural and industrial wastes into low-cost, environmentally sustainable composite materials. Mycelium composites, comprising a mycelium matrix formed through natural fungal growth and a waste-based filler have displayed significant potential as biodegradable alternatives to synthetic foams for a range of applications including packaging, insulation and construction. The primary limitation of these materials is their poor mechanical properties, originating from the weak organic constituents they comprise, incomplete fungal digestion and bonding and the presence of non-structural elements in hyphal filaments, such as cytoplasm, proteins and lipids. This study aimed to improve the mechanical performance of mycelium materials by isolating and hot-pressing the structural polymers chitin and glucan, obtained via mild chemical extraction of fungal mycelium grown on sugarcane by-product molasses. The resulting homogenous material constituted a cheap, environmentally sustainable thin film with much higher tensile strength than existing mycelium materials, potentially suitable for applications including coatings, membranes and paper.

1 INTRODUCTION

Mycelium is the vegetative growth of filamentous fungi and has been used in the production of a range of low-cost and environmentally friendly materials in recent years [1, 2]. Most of the advances in mycelium material technology focus on mycelium composites, comprising agricultural by-products or wastes bound using natural filamentous fungal growth [3-6]. These materials typically have several advantages over traditional synthetic materials, most of which are associated with their environmental sustainability. These advantages include biodegradability, low carbon footprints and a reduced energy consumption associated with their manufacture. They are also low in cost and low density, typically being characterised as foams [3, 6, 7]. A combination of non-structural elements within hyphae (e.g. cytoplasm, proteins and lipids), limited interfacial bonding and the presence of weak undigested agricultural by-products or wastes in these composite materials results in poor mechanical properties, typically ranging up to 1.1 MPa [8]. However, much higher performance mycelium materials are achievable in the form of materials derived from treated fungal biomass. The water mould *Allomyces arbuscula* is an excellent source of mycelium-derived fungal chitin, with a known high cell wall chitin concentration [9], which is linked with β -glucan. Chitin has a tensile strength significantly greater than many synthetic materials such as carbon fibres and steel due to hydrogen bonding along the chains which give them rigidity [10]. Fungal chitin is a cheap, renewable and abundant alternative to regionally limited crustacean chitin [11, 12] and can be extracted from the cell walls of hyphae within the mycelial biomass and pressed into homogenous planar materials, such as thin films. This study aimed to produce thin films from *A. arbuscula* biomass-derived biopolymers grown on the low-cost agricultural by-product sugarcane molasses. Potential applications for the thin films include coatings, composites, membranes and paper.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY

2.1 Fungal growth, biopolymer extraction and thin film preparation

A. arbuscula fungal biomass was grown for the purposes of this study in sugarcane molasses diluted using DI water (1 g/10 mL). *A. arbuscula* was selected for use based on its high chitin cell wall concentration [9] and growth performance [13] and sourced from the RMIT University fungal culture collection (Bundoora, Australia). Isolate cultures were cut into inoculum disks with a diameter of 7 mm and suspended in diluted blackstrap molasses, an exceptional fungal nutrient [14]. Fungal growth under ambient conditions (25°C) for 14 d yielded biomass which could then be separated from the diluted sugarcane molasses and processed to produce thin films (Fig. 1). Fungal biomass was washed three times and vacuum filtered before being blended for 5 min in 500 mL of water. The resulting suspension was heated to 85°C for 30 min, cooled to 25°C and centrifuged at 9000 rpm for 15 min at 18°C. The resultant residue was resuspended in a 1 M NaOH solution for 3 h at 65°C, before being again cooled and neutralised (pH 7) by repeated centrifugation and redispersion of the residue in water. Polymer extracts were then suspended in 500 mL of water, vacuum filtered (VWR 125 mm qualitative filter paper 413, particle retention 5-13 µm), peeled and cold pressed for 5 min on blotting paper between metal plates under a 5 kg mass. The extracts were finally hotpressed at 120°C for 15 min under 500 kg to achieve the final thin films.

Figure 1: Thin film production from *A. arbuscula* biopolymers. (a) fungal growth over 14 d in sugarcane molasses diluted using DI water, (b) biomasses washed and separated from diluted sugarcane molasses, (c) biomasses blended in 500 mL DI water, (d) neutralised biopolymer extract after 1M NaOH alkaline treatment, (e) vacuum filtration of biopolymer extract, (f) final thin film prior to hot pressing.

2.2 Morphological and elemental analysis

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) imaging and energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) elemental analysis of each thin film was performed using a Zeiss Supra 55 VP Scanning Electron Microscope with an Oxford X-MaxN 20 Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometer attached. An accelerating voltage of 30 kV was used. The EDS spectra were analysed using the AZtecEnergy EDS software. An average spectrum was obtained based on individual spectra from 12 different sites.

C, H, N, S and O elemental analysis was completed for triplicate 2 mg samples using a Eurovector EA 3000 CHNS-O elemental analyser. Complete digestion of (earth) alkaline elements in the samples was then completed by mineralising the samples, through combustion at 590°C, and then dissolving the residue in diluted nitric acid (pH ~3.0). The resulting solution was then filtered, and the K, Ca, Mg and Na content analysed using a PrinCE Crystal 310 Capillary Electrophoresis instrument, with detection registered using a TraceDec conductivity detector.

2.3 Analysis of molecular structure

IR spectra were recorded using a Cary 630 FT-IR instrument (Agilent) with a single reflection diamond ATR-module and potassium bromide (KBr) optical equipment. Three spectra were recorded from different portions of material to verify homogeneity. Spectra were recorded across the full accessible range from 4,000-400 cm⁻¹.

2.4 Physical and mechanical properties

The thin films were cut into dog bone shaped specimens (with dimensions based on type 1BB, BS EN ISO 527-2, 2012) using a Zwick ZCP 020 Manual Cutting Press. Specimens had a parallel width of 2 mm and an overall length of 30 mm. The thickness of each specimen was determined using an AnyiMeasuring digital outside micrometer. Tensile tests were performed using a model 5969 Instron dual column universal testing system, equipped with a 1 kN load cell and a Gig ProE iMETRIUM non-contact video extensometer. Specimens were fixed between metal clamps using blotting paper to avoid perforation of the samples. Testing velocity was 1 mm/min with gauge length set to 12 mm. The elastic modulus (E) was analysed in the linear elastic region as a secant between strength values separated by 0.2 % strain. The tensile strength (σ) was calculated from maximum load and specimen cross-sectional area.

2.5 Surface properties

The advancing contact angles of polar (water) and non-polar (diiodo-methane) test liquids on the thin films were determined using a Krüss DSA30 drop shape analyser. An initial contact angle measurement was recorded 0.5 s after dosing with double Sessile drops (3 μ L drop of each test liquid), followed by 10 drops (0.2 μ L each) dosed and measured with 0.5 s delay between each drop. A total of 100 measurements at 10 individual sites were recorded and screened individually for each thin film to ensure that droplet profiles were well formed and level. Contact angle and surface free energy were calculated using the Owens, Wendt, Rabel and Kaelble (OWRK) method [15] in the Krüss Advance software (v 1.5.1).

2.6 Thermal degradation properties

Thin film thermal degradation properties were assessed using a TA Instruments Discovery TGA. Film fragment samples of approximately 10 mg were placed in a platinum high temperature crucible and heated from 30°C to 1000°C at a heating rate of 20°C/min. Samples were tested in air and nitrogen atmospheres (both 25 mL/min).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Thin film elemental and molecular characterisation

Elemental analysis of the *A. arbuscula* thin films (Table 1) demonstrated that they primarily comprised C (47.1 wt%), O (38.6 wt%) and H (7.1 wt%), which is typical of biologically derived polymers. Only trace quantities of S (0.2 wt%) and P (0.1 wt%) were detected in the thin films.

Species	Elemental composition (wt% of total mass)									
	C	H	N	O	S	P	K	Ca	Mg	Na
<i>A. arbuscula</i> (mycelium)	47.1	7.1	1.9	38.6	0.2	0.1	0.1	4.8	0.1	0.1

Table 1. Elemental analysis for *A. arbuscula* thin films.

EDS point detect analysis (Fig 2a.) also indicated that the thin films contained significant quantities of Ca, which prompted completion of inorganic salt analysis (K, Ca, Mg and Na). This analysis identified 4.8 wt% Ca salts in the thin films, most likely derived from the molasses growth medium which contained 0.7 wt% Ca. Fungi growing in Ca rich environments are known to typically contain Ca biomineralized in hyphae as calcite (CaCO_3) and calcium oxalate [16].

N was also present in the thin films (1.9 wt%). The presence of N indicates the presence of chitin, since N is associated with the secondary amide in chitin and can be further characterised using ATR-FTIR spectroscopy.

Figure 2: (a) EDS and (b) ATR-FTIR spectra for the *A. arbuscula* thin films.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Fig 2b.) verified the presence of the chitin in the *A. arbuscula* thin films with -NH stretching visible at 3228 cm^{-1} , in addition to an amide I peak associated with C=O stretching at 1624 cm^{-1} . Amide II and III peaks, resulting from -NH deformation, were also present at 1544 cm^{-1} and 1320 cm^{-1} respectively, with the amide III peak indicating the presence of a secondary amide. The glucose monomer of the glucan and chitin polymer structure was also displayed as an -OH band at 3317 cm^{-1} , -CH peaks at 2920 cm^{-1} and 2850 cm^{-1} and a C-O-C peak at 1026 cm^{-1} .

3.2 Physical and mechanical properties

A. arbuscula had a surface and cross section with a largely obscured fiber structure (Fig. 3), biomineralized with Ca salts and interfaced with a surface layer of organic lipid residue. These contaminants most likely resulted from the use of the sugarcane molasses nutrient medium which is known to be highly impure, containing ash and minerals such as P, Ca, Mg, Na, K, Cl, S, Cu, Zn, Fe, Mn and Co [17].

Figure 3: (a) surface morphology and (b) fracture surface of *A. arbuscula* thin films.

The thin films produced in this study from biopolymers extracted from *A. arbuscula* fungal biomass significantly outperformed all known mycelium composite materials, which have been previously characterised exclusively as foams. Mycelium composites typically have low densities and elastic moduli despite physical processing such as hot pressing [5]. For example, a representative mycelium composite of *G. lucidum* growing on red oak has a density of 0.3 g/cm^3 and an elastic modulus of 1.3 MPa (foam grade material) [18]. Conversely, the *A. arbuscula* thin films produced in this study from hotpressed structural polymer extracts were characterised as polymer materials based on their elastic modulus of 1.8 GPa and density of 1.3 g/cm^3 (polymer grade material).

A. arbuscula thin films had an ultimate tensile strength of 16.0 MPa (Table 2, Figure 4). This value was significantly higher than mycelium composite materials, which typically have ultimate tensile strengths ranging from 0.01-1.1 MPa [5, 8]. Mycelium composites produced from *G. lucidum* grown on red oak have ultimate tensile strengths of approximately 0.18 MPa [18]. Overall, mycelium-derived thin film mechanical performance was comparable to commercial copy paper and some conventional plastics [19].

Species	ρ (g/cm^3)	E (GPa \pm SE)	σ_{UTS} (MPa \pm SE)	ϵ_f (% \pm SE)
<i>A. arbuscula</i> (mycelium)	1.4 ± 0.001	1.8 ± 0.4	16.0 ± 0.8	0.9 ± 0.3
Mycelium composite (<i>G. lucidum</i> on red oak)	0.3	1.3	0.18	0.07

Table 2. Density (ρ), elastic modulus (E), tensile strength (σ_{UTS}) and strain to failure (ϵ_f) of thin films produced from *A. arbuscula* mycelium and *G. lucidum* composites on red oak (data from [18]).

Figure 4. Tensile stress-strain curve for NaOH treated and hot-pressed *A. arbuscula* thin films and *G. lucidum* composites on red oak (data from [18]).

3.3 Surface properties

Thin films derived from polymers extracted from *A. arbuscula* biomass were hydrophobic, with high advancing water contact angles ($\sim 106^\circ$) (Table 3) compared to cellulose thin films, which range from $\sim 60\text{--}90^\circ$ depending on their lignin content [20, 21]. The hydrophobicity of mycelium-derived materials has previously been noted, with static water contact angles up to 122° reported [8]. The high contact angles of the thin films were associated with low surface energy values (28 mN/m). Chitin and chitosan theoretically exhibit slightly higher surface energy than other polysaccharides, such as, cellulose and starch, due to the presence of amino and amide moieties [22]. However, non-polar impurities have been noted to be responsible for lower polar surface energy components in less pure chitin [23]. Non-polar impurities responsible for the aroma of fungi, such as alcohols, lipid residues and acid derivatives are prevalent in fungal biomass [24] and may have caused the high advancing contact angles and low surface energies of the *A. arbuscula* thin films. These hydrophobic properties could make mycelium-derived thin films useful for applications including coatings.

Species	Advancing contact angle (θ_A)		Surface energy, γ (mN/m \pm SD)
	H ₂ O ($^\circ \pm$ SD)	CH ₂ I ₂ ($^\circ \pm$ SD)	
<i>A. arbuscular</i> (mycelium)	106.3 ± 6.9	60.6 ± 7.6	28.3 ± 4.6

Table 3. Advancing contact angle and surface energy of *A. arbuscula* thin films.

3.4 Thermal degradation properties

Mycelium has similar thermal degradation and fire reaction properties to most cellulosic and plant-derived materials, with lignin- or silica-based substrates primarily responsible for the fire-resistant properties of mycelium composite materials [25, 26]. A three-stage process typically occurs during the thermal degradation of mycelium beginning with the evaporation of free and chemically bonded water

from 25-200°C, associated with a mass loss of ~5 wt%. A second stage associated with a mass loss of ~70 wt% then occurs between 200-375°C, as organic constituents including proteins and polysaccharides degrade. During the final stage primary residual char degrades to form carbonaceous char residue between 450-600°C [4].

Thin films produced from polymers extracted from *A. arbuscula* biomass exhibited a similar three-stage degradation process and a char residue of ~20 wt% in a nitrogen atmosphere (Fig. 5). This was characteristic of mycelium, which has been previously noted to yield char residues of ~23 wt% in nitrogen atmospheres [4, 8]. The thin films did not fully thermally decompose in air atmospheres, but rather yielded an inorganic residue of ~8 wt%, which was attributable to the calcium content of their biomineralized hyphae.

Figure 5. TGA mass loss curve of *A. arbuscula* thin films in nitrogen and air atmospheres.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Fungi provide a unique opportunity to convert low-cost agricultural by-products, such as sugarcane molasses, into biopolymers such as chitin. These biopolymers can then be used to produce materials such as thin films, which exhibit significantly better mechanical performance than mycelium composite materials comprising agricultural waste fillers bound using a fibrous mycelium matrix. While comprising primarily chitin and glucan, the mycelium-derived thin films also contained inorganic calcium salt and lipid residue contaminants, which influenced the mechanical, surface and thermal properties of the thin films. The hydrophobic properties of the thin films could make them suitable for coating applications, while their tensile properties could make them a suitable alternative to paper and some plastics. These findings coupled with the diverse variety of fungal species and growth media in existence suggest the potential for low-cost, waste-derived mycelium materials with tunable properties for a wide range of applications.

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